

Awareness, Attitude and Preventive Practices of Students and Faculty About Occupational Hazards In a Public Teaching Hospital of Fasilabad, Pakistan.

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Abstract:

Aims: *To assess the level of awareness, attitude and preventive practices related to occupational hazards in dental students and faculty of a public teaching hospital of Faisalabad, Pakistan.*

Material and method: *The present study was conducted at a public teaching hospital of Faisalabad, Pakistan by using self-administered questionnaires. All the students and faculty members of the hospital were invited to participate in the study. The total study population consisted of 300 dental professionals. The self-administered questionnaire contains questions of personal information like age, gender, position (student or faculty), number of working hours per day apart from the questions on the level of awareness, preventive procedures undertaken and occupational hazards experienced.*

Results: *Significantly greater number of students experienced musculoskeletal disorders than dental faculty. Nearly half the study population reported of sharp instrument injury while treating the patients. The most prevalent preventive measure reported by the respondents was changing gloves between the patients (100%) and use of face mask (80.6%). Most of the participants (72.4%) had undergone Hepatitis B or other vaccination procedures.*

Conclusion: *Majority of the study population was aware of the biological hazards associated with the practice of dentistry. But not all preventive measures were observed by all the participants.*

Key word: *occupational hazards, Dental personnel, prevention, dental injury*

Introduction:

Occupational hazard can be defined as the risk to the health of a person usually arising out of employment. It can also refer to work, material, substance, process or situation that predisposes or itself causes accidents or disease at work place[1]. Health hazards related to work place are very common[2]. Although modern dentistry now a day considered least hazards profession[3] but many risk factors still present in current dental practices which continue to challenge this status.

Dentists are exposed to various occupational hazards like allergic reactions, work related stress, higher noise levels, sharp instrument injuries, radiation, musculoskeletal disorders, etc. [4]. In addition to these hazards dental persons are also exposed with various microorganisms like hepatitis and HIV .[5] These Infectious agents may be transmitted through blood or saliva, as a result of bacteremia or viremia associated with systemic infections. Assessment of professional hazards among dentists is therefore an important aspect of dental profession.[6]

Related to prevention, the international literature focuses on infection control, proper barrier techniques and proper handling of potentially infected materials, owing to the high profile of dentistry regarding transmission of infection. Barrier techniques include gloves, masks, high power suction, protective eye wear, and good ventilation to decrease aerosols and vapor dangers[7]. Hypoallergenic non-latex gloves are proposed to deal with latex allergy. Lead aprons, periodic maintenance of the X-ray machine and radiation level sensors prevent radiation hazards[8]

Long term exposure to occupational hazards causes illnesses that are specific to the profession, which develop and exaggerate over the years. In many cases they result in diseases and disease complexes, some of which are regarded as occupational illnesses[9]

Hence, the present study was aimed to assess the awareness, attitude and preventive measures related to occupational hazards by the students and faculty working at a public dental teaching hospital in Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Material and method:

This is a cross-sectional, questioner-based study conducted among the dental students (1st, 2nd, 3rd & 4th year) and faculty of dental section Faisalabad medical university, Faisalabad. The duration of study was two months from October to November 2019. Before the study approval of ethical committee of Faisalabad medical university, Faisalabad was taken. The time for fill the questioner was approximately 10 min for each participants and Informed consent obtained from each participant.

Sample size:

Total of 300 participants take part in the study out of which only 290 questioners were completely filled and included in study.

Inclusion and exclusive criteria:

All the students and faculty members who were voluntarily agreed to take part in study are included.

Questioner:

After the literature review and expert's opinion a questioner of 17 closed and open-ended question were prepared. The questioner has four main sections. In first section demographic details were taken. In second section knowledge about occupational hazards were asked. In third section preventive measures and in last section experienced occupational hazards were asked.

Statistical analysis:

The data obtained from questioner was analyzed in SPSS version 21 software and presented in the form of frequency and percentage tables

Results:

A total of 300 participants 210 (70%) were dental students and 90 participants were under dental faculty. The out of 300 questioners only 290 were completely filled and included in final result of study. Out of 290 students 150 are female and rest are males. 100 dental persons work more than five hours daily. 50 (17.2%) participants also do private dental clinic along working with public Hospital.

Regarding the awareness related to occupational hazards 250 (86.2%) participants have basic concept about the occupational hazards in dentistry and only 50 (17.2%) participants attend any workshop or seminar on occupational hazards. 150 (51.7%) participants have proper knowledge about hepatitis B, C viruses and their different modes of transmission. 200 (68.9%) dental persons properly placed the sharp instruments and needle in separate container (Table 1)

For the preventive measures, 290 (100%) participants change their gloves after examining every patient. 180 (62.0%) participants wear protective eyewear and 120 (41.3%) dental persons wash their hand after performing dental procedure. 260 (89.7%) wear mask for every dental procedure. Only 190 (65.5%) participants change their position for working in different quadrants. 210 (72.4%) are vaccinated from hepatitis B. 220 (75.8%) dental persons take proper medical history from patient. Only 30 (10.3%) participants properly dispose their left over mercury (Table 2)

Table 1: Knowledge or awareness about occupational hazards

Variables	students	faculty	total	percentage
attended any workshop or seminar	0	50	50	17.2
Awareness of mode of transmission Of HBV, HCV	60	90	150	51.7
dispose of needle or Sharpe instrument	130	70	200	68.9
Recap anesthesia syringe after use	50	90	140	48.3

Table 2: Preventive measures undertaken by the study population against the occupational hazards

Preventive measures	Students	Faculty	Total	percentage
Change of gloves after every patient	200	90	290	100
Use of protective eyewear	150	30	180	62.0
Wash of hand after every dental procedure	50	70	120	41.4
Wearing mask	190	70	260	80.6
Change of working position	100	90	190	65.5
Hepatis B vaccination	150	60	210	72.4
Taking complete medical history of patient	140	80	220	75.8
Dispose of left-over mercury	20	10	30	10.3

More than half of subjects experienced some kind of stress, either it be patient related, dentist related or economic. 230 (79.3%) of the participants had musculoskeletal disorders which are more common in dental students. It was interesting to note that nearly half of the study population reported sharp instrument injury while treating the patients. 190(65.5%) of the responder faces needle stick injury or injury from sharp instrument during their practicing period. Only 6(2.0%) responders reported the latex allergy or allergy from any dental material. (Table 3)

Table 3: Occupational hazards experienced by students and faculty

Variables	frequency	Percentage (%)
Stress		
patient related	100	48.1
dentist related	20	38.6
economic	40	10.6
physical hazards		
musculoskeletal pain	230	79.3%
needle stick injury	190	65.5%
latex allergy	6	2.0%

Discussion:

A cross sectional, questioner-based study[10] conducted at a public teaching hospital of Faisalabad, Pakistan. Both students and dental faculty participated in study. It is a proven fact that Dentistry is a profession that involves different risk and constant exposure to human infectious agents, and stress and other occupational injuries[11].Despite the various advancement in dentistry the occupational hazards are still present in the field of dentistry.

In the present study the view point of dental students and dental faculty were asked. Majority of dental student and dentists are aware of the fact that occupational hazards are present in dental practice. Education is one of the important strategies for the prevention of occupational injuries and diseases. But a very few numbers (17.2%) of dentist attend any seminar or workshop on occupational hazards which is very alarming situation. Because proper knowledge about the hazards is necessary to reduce the hazards associated with dental practice. In dentistry clinical staff is always in contact with saliva or blood in direct or in direct contact[12].Oral health care professional may get infection by a cut, wound or a needle stick injury etc. In order to reduce the risk of getting infection a proper knowledge and awareness of different infectious agents and their mode of transmission is necessary. In current study (51.7%) of participant has knowledge about the HBV and HCV virus transmission. About the knowledge, dental faculty more aware than dental students.

Sharp instrument and needle are the major cause of needle stick injuries which can transmit the different infectious agents to the victim blood. In the United States more than 800,000 needle stick injuries occur each year. About 65.5% responder reported these injuries. the main causes of the injury are the poor handling of these objects but only 68.9%participants properly dispose of sharp instruments or needles after use.

In dentistry dental amalgam is excessively used material. Different studies reported about the toxicity of mercury which is the basic component of dental amalgam[13]. So properly dispose of the left-over mercury is necessary but only 10.3% participant properly dispose of the mercury which is very low percentage. so proper awareness about mercury hazards are required.

Concerning preventive measures, about all the dentist (100%)wear gloves and change their gloves after every procedure but only (80.2 %)responder reported the use of protective mask which contradict with the East Jerusalem study were all the responder use protective barrier clothing[11].

Eye injuries causes by projectiles such as bits of calculus during scaling procedures and splatters from body fluids (bacterial and viral aerosols) while using high-speed hand pieces. Another potential source of eye injury is the intense dental curing light. Use of protective eyewear is advice to avoid all such injuries but only (62.0%) participant uses protective eyewear during practicing dentistry.

In dental practice, dentist assumes a strained posture both while standing and sitting close to the patient who remains in a sitting or a lying position. This overstress negatively affects the musculoskeletal system [14]. In the present study, more than half (79.3%) of the respondents had musculoskeletal disorders.so posture changing while working in different quadrants in necessary but only (65.5%) subjects change their position in different quadrants. In the study it is clear that students are more suffer from musculoskeletal disorder of the neck, upper back and shoulders which is the same result of study of dentists in Queensland, Austria.[15] A proper learning about the sitting position or practice to work in indirect vision for maxillary teeth is also a key point to reduce the musculoskeletal pain .

Stress associated with work is closely related to dentist's profession. More or less, half of the study subjects experienced some kind of stress, either it be patient related or dentist related or economic. The patient related stress was normally associated with dealing with patients who had a medical history of other conditions and the possibility of the patient deliberately or unintentionally concealing their health status[11].a proper medical history taking and complete knowledge about the management of medically compromised patient can reduce the level of patient related stress. In the current study (48.1%) responder claims to have patient related stress during practicing dentistry. unethical competition among the dentists are the basic cause of dentist-dentist related stress. (38.6%) study subjects

also reported this type of stress. Professional attitude among the colleagues and healthy competition can reduce the dentist related stress.

Dental treatment is considered an expensive treatment[16] but due to increasing competition in this field ,dentists faces economical stress. 10.6% dentists reported this and it is the main consideration of faculty rather than dental students.

In dental profession, dental staff is at risk to get needle stick injuries while working sharp instruments contaminated with blood or other fluids and thus there is an ample opportunity for inadvertent skin wounds with possibility of Hepatitis and HIV transmission. So, vaccination from hepatis B is necessary to protect themselves to get infection. but only (72.4%) responder is vaccinated against hepatis B virus. Which contradict with the study of Indian Navy dentists where all responder were vaccinated [17]but in East Jerusalem study only 38% were vaccinated.[11]

In conclusion, this study showed that although there appears to be an awareness of exposure to occupational hazards among the dental students and faculty of public teaching hospital of Faisalabad, Pakistan, but more awareness is still required to prevent these hazards. It is, therefore, recommended to arrange regular workshops and seminars on occupational hazards in institution so that students and faculty can update their knowledge and, hopefully, influence their work practices.

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